

THE IMPORTANCE OF COMPARATIVE-ANALYTICAL STUDY OF EDUCATIONAL METHODOLOGIES IN ACHIEVING SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: Human capital is the main foundation of sustainable development. Education is an important tool for developing human knowledge and skills, raising social awareness, and achieving the goals of sustainable development. In this article, different educational methodologies and their contribution to the goals of sustainable development are studied on the basis of comparative analysis. The importance of educational methodologies in achieving these goals and their use in the modern educational process are discussed.

Key words: Sustainable development, educational methodologies, comparative analysis, active education, problem-based education, virtual education, online platforms, UN, sustainable development goals, educational effectiveness.

Introduction.

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) adopted by the United Nations (UN) in 2015 are aimed at finding solutions to the most pressing issues facing humanity and our planet [3]. These 17 goals to be achieved by 2030 include ending poverty, ending hunger, improving health care, providing quality education, combating climate change, and other global challenges. Achieving these goals depends not only on the government and state policy, but also on the systematic organization of scientific research. In this sense, a number of measures are being implemented in our country to achieve BRM. An example of this is the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to accelerate the implementation of national goals and tasks in the field of sustainable development until 2030" [1].

This article discusses the effective organization of BRM-oriented research and its implementation.

Systematic organization of research

Factors such as strategic planning, resource management, scientific cooperation, monitoring and evaluation play an important role in the systematic organization of BRM-oriented research.

Strategic planning

Since each BRM includes specific tasks, it is necessary to define specific goals and objectives before starting research. Researchers should choose scientific directions that are compatible with BRM and implement programmatic planning for them [2].

Resource management

Effectiveness of scientific research requires proper management of financial, human and technical resources. It is important to effectively use the financial support of state organizations, international donors and the private sector. It is also necessary to ensure the success of research by training scientific personnel and providing them with the necessary resources.

Scientific cooperation

Since BRM-oriented research involves multifaceted and sectoral issues, it is important to establish cooperation between research institutions, universities, governmental and non-governmental organizations. International scientific cooperation is important in increasing the effectiveness of research. For example, it is necessary to cooperate between scientists and institutions from different countries in international studies on the education system. International scientific cooperation is widely established at Ma'mun University, where the university signs memorandums with international higher education institutions to create opportunities for scientific cooperation between scientists.

Monitoring:

By evaluating and monitoring the results of research, it is possible to measure the effectiveness of work in the process of achieving the goals of BRM. Statistical data, indicators and analytical methods are used in this process. The results of monitoring provide a basis for making adjustments to research and developing new strategies.

Implementation of research results

The main goal of BRM-oriented research is to apply the obtained results in practice. The results of scientific research can be put into practice in the following ways:

Formation of state policy

Based on the results of the research, the recommendations can be used in determining the policies of the governments on sustainable development. For example, climate change research helps in the formation and development of environmental protection legislation.

BRM-oriented research creates new opportunities and business models for the private sector. For example, on the basis of research conducted on renewable energy sources, enterprises based on solar or wind energy can be established [5].

By sharing research results at the international level, there will be an opportunity to exchange experience between countries and regions. This will serve to accelerate the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals set by the UN.

As noted, sustainable development is an approach aimed at ensuring the living conditions of future generations by harmoniously meeting the ecological, economic and social needs of mankind. Most of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals set by the UN are closely related to education. The importance of education in achieving these goals shows the need to develop it using different methodologies. Therefore, the comparative-analytical study of educational methodologies is gaining importance. In this regard, a number of practical works are being carried out at Ma'mun University. In particular, work is being carried out to ensure the participation of students in international scientific and practical conferences, scientific exchanges, international conferences and joint educational programs.

The link between sustainable development and education.

The role of education in achieving sustainable development can be considered in three main directions:

1. Development of knowledge and skills: For sustainable development, it is important to develop environmental literacy, economic and social skills at all levels of the population. Education contributes to the establishment of a sustainable way of life in society by forming these knowledge and skills.

2. Changing mindsets and social consciousness: Achieving sustainable development requires a rethinking of people's lifestyles, needs and values. One of the main tasks of education is to change people's thinking and teach them to make decisions with a sense of social responsibility.

3. Innovation support: It is necessary to introduce new technologies and innovations in solving modern problems. The education system can accelerate the process of sustainable development by teaching innovative approaches.

Analysis of educational methodologies.

Educational methodologies used to achieve sustainable development have different characteristics. Their comparative and analytical study is important for increasing efficiency and improving educational systems.

Traditional educational methodology.

Traditional educational methodology is based on lectures, textbooks and the leading role of the teacher. Basic theoretical knowledge is provided through this methodology. The traditional methodology has a special place in teaching the basic concepts of sustainable development goals.

The comparative and analytical study of educational methodologies in achieving sustainable development is important in the following aspects:

1. *Choosing an appropriate approach:* Through comparative-analytical study, it is possible to analyze the advantages and disadvantages of different educational methodologies. This will help in choosing the appropriate educational approach for BRM.

2. *Improving the effectiveness of methodologies:* As a result of a comparative study of the methodologies used in the educational process, certain changes can be made to increase their effectiveness.

3. *Introduction of innovative approaches:* Through a comparative-analytical approach, it is possible to find ways to ensure the harmony of traditional and modern educational methodologies and to introduce innovative educational technologies.

The role of education in achieving sustainable development is incomparable. A comparative-analytical study of educational methodologies allows to determine how effective they are in achieving the goals of sustainable development. Traditional, active, problem-based and virtual learning methodologies have their own advantages and disadvantages, and it is necessary to use them appropriately. At the same time, modern and innovative educational processes by combining different educational methodologies.

Conclusion.

Scientific research is of great importance in achieving the UN's Sustainable Development Goals. By systematically organizing research, countries, organizations and communities can take important steps towards achieving the MDGs. Factors such as strategic planning, effective use of resources, scientific cooperation and monitoring of results play an important role in the success of research. Also, by implementing the research results, the possibilities of achieving the main tasks of BRM will be expanded.

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